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Impact of the Economic Crisis on Service Delivery: A Case Study of the Hospitality Sector in Victoria Falls, Zimbabwe

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Abstract

Since 2000, the economy of Zimbabwe has been characterised by an unprecedented hyper-inflation since the country attained its Independence. The hyperinflation has impacted negatively on virtually all economic sectors in the country, including the hospitality industry. As a result, the hospitality industry has experienced an unprecedented exodus of skilled and experienced workers who have continued to depart to neighbouring countries, particularly South Africa and Zambia. The purpose of this study, therefore, was to assess the impact of this exodus on service delivery in the prime resort town of Victoria Falls. To obtain data, the study utilized both quantitative and qualitative approaches of data collection from clients, employees and management. The assessment revealed that, since 2000, the hospitality sector at the resort town of Victoria Falls has been undergoing a major decline in the quality of service delivery to their clients. The poor service delivery is attributed to inexperienced employees who were recruited during the crisis period and are, therefore, not experienced to serve efficiently at that level. This, in turn, has been exacerbated by failure on the part of the hospitality sector to invest in training of the new and inexperienced recruits. As a result, most visitors to Victoria Falls, except for business tourists, are day excursionists who have opted to either fly back or spend to the night across the Zambezi River in Livingstone, Zambia. The study concluded that service delivery is a critical factor in ensuring customer satisfaction and service experience as well as in attracting long-term clients. Thus, there is need for the hospitality industry in general and in Victoria Falls in particular, to re-brand itself through continuous training and education of employees.

Keywords: hospitality industry, economic crisis, hyperinflation, service delivery, rebranding.

1.0 Introduction

An economic crisis can affect all sectors of the economy within a country (Primorac, 2012). From the year 2000, Zimbabwe experienced a serious political and economic crisis which virtually brought the country to its knees. In 1999, the Zimbabwe Government launched its Land Reform Program whereby land was violently taken from white commercial farmers, including from those with Zimbabwean citizenship, and given to indigenous black Zimbabweans, some of whom had very little experience in commercial farming. The violence, instability and insecurity that followed had an immediate adverse impact on the economy of the country. According to Power (2003), the once breadbasket of Africa deteriorated to such an extent that it became the continent's basket case. The economy was characterised by high inflation which at its peak in 2008, was estimated at 231 million percent. This in turn, led to a decline in capacity utilisation, decreased production, shortages of almost all basic products and services, and the departure to other countries of both skilled and unskilled labour force. This situation also impacted negatively on the country's tourism and hospitality industry.

The tourism sector recorded an 11% drop in tourist arrivals and a 38% decrease in tourism receipts (Zimbabwe Tourism Authority, 2000). The downward trend continued in the years that followed, thereby impacting negatively on the contribution of the tourism sector to the GDP. It is important to note that tourism is a highly sensitive industry that responds either positively or negatively to changes in a destination area. It is an industry which does not depend only on the presence of world wonders, the existence of wonderful national parks and the big five, or efficient transport services and modern technological changes. Thus, while Victoria Falls and indeed Zimbabwe at large still boasted of a beautiful climate, outstanding game parks and world class facilities and hotels, the violence and general political instability that followed the Land Reform Programme as well as the 2002 and 2008 presidential and parliamentary elections brought about feelings of insecurity among most international tourists, thereby severely damaging tourism and the hospitality industry of the country, leading to an unprecedented exodus of the sector's most skilled and experienced employees.

Although occasional improvements were recorded in 2005, 2006 and 2007, due to the sector's efforts to manage the country's damaged image, the contribution of the hospitality industry to the GDP still remained negative. The re-surfacing of political instability during the 2008 general elections, once again resulted in the deterioration of the sector, thereby overpowering the image building efforts that had been implemented in the previous two years.

1.2 Research Problem

The economic crisis in Zimbabwe negatively impacted all sectors of the economy, but the hospitality industry was particularly hard hit. As the crisis deepened, many hotels and restaurants lost business, leading to several closures or down-sizing of operations, followed by labour retrenchments and loss of skilled and experienced employees. Although the hospitality industry has frequently been used by researchers to provide empirical evidence on the effects of crises, research on service delivery has been limited. This study was, therefore, prompted by this information gap. Thus, the purpose of the study was to assess the level of service quality to the patrons in the hospitality industry at the Victoria Falls resort town. To achieve this purpose, the study applied the SERVQUAL model which focuses on five dimensions, namely, *reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy and responsiveness* (RATER).

1.3 Research objectives

The main objective of this study was to assess the impact of the Zimbabwe economic crisis on service delivery within the Hospitality Sector in Victoria Falls. Specifically, the study focused on the level of customer satisfaction using the following five (5) dimensions or attributes:

- a) Responsiveness;
- b) Assurance;
- c) Tangibility or tangibles;
- d) Empathy; and,
- e) Reliability.

1.4 Main Research Question

1. **What is the impact of the Zimbabwe economic crisis on the quality of service delivery in the hospitality industry in the resort town of Victoria Falls?**

2.0 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 What is a crisis?

According to Ozcan et al. (2012), a crisis is an unfortunate, adverse and tough period of time endured by a person, organization or nation. It impedes the achievement of a nation's objectives and puts the nation at risk. Crises can either emanate from natural causes or can be human motivated. The effects of these different types of crises can be at local, national, regional and global scales, depending on their magnitude. For example, the most popular Asian crisis of 1997 affected economies in the Asian Pacific Region whilst the recent 2008 world economic crisis had an effect on economies the world over. Additionally, there are other crises such as the United States September, 11th 2001 terrorist attacks and the war in Iraq that received a lot of global publicity.

2.2 The Service Quality Model or SERVQUAL

The SERVQUAL Model is a multiple item scales for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality. According to Oliva and Stermann (2001), service quality is a function of customers' expectations and the time allocated per customer. The authors explain that the time taken to serve a customer determines the level of attention and care that an individual customer will receive. They further note that customer experience with a service is determined by the level of skills that an organization's employees have. This they term service capacity. Oliva and Stermann (2001) then came up with equations that can be used to calculate the level of service quality and service capacity and these were tested with a service organization. The model by the authors was a major improvement of the RATER model that was developed by Parasuraman in 1988. This research, therefore, uses the Oliva and Stermann (2001) model to assess service quality and experiences of the hospitality sector clients in Victoria Falls.

According to Chow-Chua and Kamaran (2002), one characteristic of service delivery in the tourism and hospitality sector, and indeed in other sectors, is that there is simultaneous production and consumption, implying that services are produced and consumed at the same time in the presence of the customer and the service producer. This makes employees crucial in determining the quality of service experienced by the consumer. Some writers have gone further to relate employees' expertise to the level of service quality a customer experiences.

2.3 Service Delivery Assessment

In a study conducted to evaluate how the level of employee expertise affects customer experience, Oliva and Sterman (2001) argue that customers are satisfied with service delivery if employees are skilled and are not rushed by the servers. However, during an economic crisis, this requirement may prove difficult to observe. According to Invernizzi and Hallewel (2006), during the economic crisis in Brazil, labour market conditions deteriorated as labour preferred self-employment and employment in the informal sector. In Zimbabwe, Kanyenze (2011) found that formal-sector employment declined from the peak of 1.4 million in 1999 to an estimated 700 000 by 2007. In the tourism and hospitality industry, research has noted that servicescape is an important construct for service organizations. According to Leiper and Hing (1998), during the Asian Crisis, there was a sharp downturn in investment in the tourism sector of all the countries in the Asian Pacific Region.

In order to effectively evaluate service quality, it is safer to first assess consumers' *expectations* prior to the service encounter with a product, and then compare the *perceptions* they will have developed during or after the delivery of that service.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DESIGN

3.1 Data Collection

The study was based on expectations and actual experiences of clients in the hotels and restaurants of the Victoria Falls resort town. The research adopted both quantitative and qualitative approaches. A questionnaire with 44 attributes was distributed to measure service quality after the economic crisis. Interviews were also held with both hotel managers and employees to get explanations to some of the responses from the consumers of their services. To complement the data from the respondents, the researchers also used their own impressions with service delivery in two different hotels.

3.2. Sampling and Instrumentation

A total of 210 local and foreign tourists responded to the questionnaire, whilst interviews were conducted with four managers, 10 employees and 20 corporate clients. The questionnaire was the major instrument in this research. The researchers adopted a questionnaire developed by Kandampully et al (2001) and adapted it in line with the objectives of the study thus allowing the researchers to measure the service experience of clients during the economic crisis in Zimbabwe. The instrument had 44 items addressing the 5 attributes of the RATER Model. The questionnaire was divided into sections A and B. Section A measured the customers' expectations of the hotel sector service delivery, while Section B measured customer perceptions of the service delivery. Discussions with management were then held to validate experiences as narrated by the patrons themselves. Interviews were held with hotel employees to establish the hotel's staff complement (both skilled and unskilled) hired during the crisis. Qualitative data from these interviews together with the researchers' own experiences from hotel service encounters were used to explain questionnaire responses from the customers.

3.3 Data analysis procedure

Interviews were analyzed by drawing a number of key themes that emerged from the discussions and comparison of interviewee responses was made. SPSS was used to analyse quantitative data from the questionnaires. The 44 questionnaire items were grouped into the 5 attributes of measuring service quality. To analyse service quality and customers' level of dissatisfaction, Oliva & Sterman (1988) econometric model was adopted and modified.

3.4 Calculating Service Quality Experience Using Oliva and Sterman (2001) Model

The SERVQUAL Model assumes that service quality (q) is a non-linear function of the experience between the time allocated per order (T) and customers' expectations. The Model also assumes that customer expectations are modelled as customers' beliefs regarding the effective time that should be allocated to each order (T_C) (Oliva and Sterman, 2001). Hence the authors came up with the formula below.

$$q = f_q \left(\frac{T - T_C}{T_C} \right)$$

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study revealed that there was a gradual increase in tourism employment, from 6,000 in 1980 to 23,533 in 1999. However, the year 2000 marked the beginning of a serious downturn in visitor numbers, leading to the closure and downsizing of a number of tourist and hospitality establishments, and the retrenchment of workers.

4.1 Customer Expectations

For all the 5 attributes of Service Quality, and on a scale of 1 – 5, where 1 equals strongly disagree and 5 equals strongly agree, the researchers recorded the customer expectations before landing in Victoria Falls. The expectations were responsiveness, assurance, tangibility or tangibles, empathy, and reliability.

4.1.1. Responsiveness

According to Buttle (1996), responsiveness expresses the willingness to help customers and provide prompt service. Thus expected responsiveness from staff was measured in terms of staff knowledge to answer patron's enquiries; hotel's opening hours, staff having patron's best interest and their ability to understand customers' needs. Table 4.1 gives the customers' responses with respect to their expectations before coming to Victoria Falls.

Table 4.1: Expected Responsiveness of Staff

Expectations	Mean	Std Error of Mean	Std deviation	Variance
Staff knowledge	4.3905	.06851	.99275	.986
Convenience of opening hours	4.4905	.05855	.84853	.720
Interests of patrons	4.3429	.08006	1.16017	1.346
Understanding customer needs	4.4190	.05122	.74218	.551

With an average mean of 4.410725, it is clear that customers' expectations before coming to Victoria Falls were very high. The respondents' perceptions of staff responsiveness during and after the visit were different. The mean scores of their impressions and perceptions of Victoria Falls were 2.4619 for staff knowledge; 2.5619 for opening hours; 2.3190 for patron interests; and 2.3714 for understanding customer needs, giving an average mean of only 2.42855. Some patrons stated that when they returned to their hotels after 10 pm, they did not get any service. Others complained that "Room Service" after 8 pm was not available and, in some instances, meals were hard to get. The majority of the managers agreed and explained that they had downsized their labour force in order to reduce labour costs. As a result, the few remaining employees were overwhelmed by customer expectations.

Interviews with staff confirmed that staff was aware of their inability to respond to customer needs satisfactorily. In some instances, they would tell customers that the person responsible for attending to their queries and requests was unavailable. The interests of the patrons were not prioritized by staff. In one hotel, there were no arrangements to address the problems of regular water shortages. As a consequence, some patrons had to do with the bucket system in restrooms.

4.1.2 Assurance

Assurance is defined by the knowledge and courteousness of employees and their ability to convey trust and confidence. Therefore, to determine the level of service assurance that customers expected, staff behaviour and courtesy when serving patrons were used. Similarly, patrons' feelings of safety when transacting with a hotel were the metrics used to determine the level of service assurance that customers expect from hotels.

Table 4.2: Expected Service Assurance from Staff

Expectations	Mean	Std Error of Mean
Patrons' confidence	4.5048	.07184
Patrons' feeling of security	4.6429	.05363
Staff courtesy to patrons	4.3857	.07781

The above mean scores suggest that patrons highly valued the attribute of assurance in hotel service delivery. However, during their stay in Victoria Falls, the patrons' ratings of service experiences with respect to the three (3) different constructs of service assurance were very low (See Table 4.3 below).

Table 4.3 Actual Service Assurance from staff

Expectations	Mean	Std Error of Mean
Patrons' confidence	2.5095	.07309
Patrons' feeling of security	1.9190	.04906
Staff courtesy to patrons	2.3048	.06159

The above low rating produced a very low mean score of 1.9, contrary to the original expectations of visitors. Subsequent interviews with the patrons revealed that they did not feel safe when transacting with hotel staff. They expressed concern over the billing system as they strongly felt that the prices charged for services were rather too exorbitant. They stated that they had made their bookings based on quotations that had been obtained upon enquiry from the hotel. However, on arrival, they found that the charges had increased or even doubled in some cases. Some clients felt that their valuables and personal belongings were not safe.

In response to these allegations, hotel managers confirmed these misfortunes and explained that the crisis period was a difficult period for the hotels due to the extreme poverty of their employees. As a consequence, some employees were no longer trustworthy. On their part, employees admitted that the level of poverty in the country led to some of them inflating prices so as to pocket the 'extra dollars' for their own use. The impoverished condition of the employees and fatigue from the excess duties were identified as the contributing factors towards unbecoming behaviour by their staff. It is these customer experiences that explain the low ratings of the constructs displayed in Table 4.3 above.

4.1.3 Tangibles

Tangibles refer to the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, staff grooming and any other communication materials. On this attribute, customer expectations were rated as shown in Table 4.4 below.

Table 4.4 Customer Expectations on Tangibles

Expectations	Mean	Std Error of Mean
Modern looking equipment	4.7381	.03654
Visual appeal of physical facilities	4.8762	.02278
Staff appearance	4.8857	.02201
Materials associated with service	4.5381	.04533

The mean scores for the four characteristics of tangibles ranged from 4.5381 to 4.7381. The high rankings indicate the importance attached by patrons to the construct of physical appearance. In Table 4.5 below, we display the mean scores of customer perceptions of the four physical constructs used to determine patron experiences.

Table 4.5 Customer Perceptions on Tangibles

Expectations	Mean	Std Error of Mean
Modern looking equipment	2.7714	.857
Visual appeal of physical facilities	2.5857	.665
Staff appearance	2.8048	.904
Materials associated with service	3.0952	1.063

The mean scores for the four variables are all above 2.5, indicating the mediocre appearance of buildings, equipment, staff and other hotel materials. Some patrons highlighted that the buildings were still in a fair condition but lacked maintenance. However, the lawns were not green; air conditioners were not working; and stains of dirt could be seen on carpets. Others said that some hotels had been turned into public drinking places where illegal money changers frequented. Other patrons expressed disappointment with frequent power outages, leading to dark hallways and rooms. Candle-lit dinners had become common in Victoria Falls because of power outages.

4.1.4 Empathy

Empathy is the ability to understand other peoples' circumstances, points of view, thoughts, and feelings. It considers the provision of caring, and individualized attention to customers. It is a selfless act, a desirable skill beneficial to ourselves, others and society. When experiencing empathy, we are able to understand someone else's internal experiences. Thus, Table 4.6 indicates the expectations of patrons before and during they stay in Victoria Falls.

Table 4.6 Customer Expectations on Empathy

Expectations from staff	Mean
Tell exactly when service will be offered	4.4667
Give prompt service	4.6952
Willingness to help patrons	4.7048
Never too busy to respond	4.3619
Give individualized attention	4.2810
Give personal attention	4.1905

In this study, an average score of 4.45 was calculated for customer expectations with respect to empathy.

Table 4.7 Customer Perceptions on Empathy

Expectations from staff	Mean
Tell exactly when service will be offered	1.65
Give prompt service	2.10
Willingness to help patrons	2.72
Never too busy to respond	2.74
Give individualized attention	2.16
Give personal attention	2.19

Patron perceptions regarding staff empathy was pegged at 2.26. The mean figure for time service was the lowest at 1.65. From the interviews, one patron said: "You place an order and it takes forever to be fulfilled". Another said he telephoned for room service but was only offered the service hours later when he was already in bed. Other patrons complained about lack of personalised service. They said that if *a la carte* was served, when meals were brought, they were the same for every customer. One interviewee narrated her ordeal when she had to go to bed on an empty stomach as the hotel had run out of food.

4.1.5 Reliability

Reliability relates to the ability to perform the promised service dependably. In this regard, expectations on service reliability for customers were rated fairly high at above 4 (See Table 4.8 below).

Table 4.8 Customer Expectations of Service Reliability

Expectations from staff	Mean
Promise to do something by a certain time	4.6143
Show genuine interest to solve a problem	4.8000
Perform service right first time	4.6714
Provide service at the promised time	4.6000
Insist on error-free service	4.2810

However, customer experiences during and after the visits were contrary to expectations and were rated quite low, giving an average mean score of 2.10284, as shown in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9 Customer Perceptions of Service Reliability

Expectations from staff	Mean
Promise to do something by a certain time	2.0857
Show genuine interest to solve a problem	2.1952
Perform service right first time	1.9571
Provide service at the promised time	2.1524
Insist on error-free service	2.1238

The above findings of the study indicate that there has been a general decline, if not deterioration of services in Victoria Falls since the beginning of the economic crisis in the year 2000. By factoring the impact of the economic crisis in Zimbabwe, the researchers estimated that the service quality at the Victoria Falls resort town might have declined even lower to 0.86163.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion of the study is that the quality of service delivery within the hospitality industry at the Victoria Falls declined significantly during the Zimbabwe economic crisis and that the resort town has not yet come out of the woods. This has made it virtually impossible for the industry to offer world class facilities to its patrons. This is partly explained by the industry's inability to offer a variety of menus to the clients and partly by the unavailability of a skilled and experienced labour force. These findings are in agreement with Oliva and Sterman (2001) that service delivery heavily depends on employees' level of experience.

To an extent, the industry also contributed to the experiences suffered by their patrons. Owners and management were aware of the deteriorating customer experiences but were not pro-active. They took a "stand and watch" attitude and depended on the efforts of the country's tourism marketing authority to strategise and market the country on their behalf. Yet, during an economic crisis, every sector has to play its role. For example, the industry could have paid their employees in foreign currency since the hospitality charges were in foreign currency. This way, they could have retained their experienced personnel, at least some of them. Clearly, hospitality managers were not forward looking. Yet, experience has taught us that no matter how prolonged a crisis may be, it will one day come to an end.

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